

Announcing ERGA Community Genomes on GoAT

Prepared by the ERGA Executive Board, 05-06 2025

This document describes the necessary steps and procedures for ERGA Members to announce their ERGA Community Genome Projects on the Earth BioGenome Project's (EBP) Genomes on a Tree (GoAT) portal: <https://goat.genomehubs.org/projects/ERGA-COM>

The aim is to encourage early sharing of information about the species that ERGA Members are working on to produce reference genomes, using the same GoAT portal where larger initiatives such as EBP Affiliate Projects also share information about the species on which they are working.

The motivation for announcing target species openly and early is to avoid duplicated efforts and wasted resources, as well as to promote collaborations and opportunities for new synergies. It often takes quite some time to produce a reference assembly and deposit it in public repositories. Without announcing genome generation projects on GoAT there is no public visibility of these efforts until the assembly is finally deposited in a public database. Therefore, the best way to identify potential overlaps is to announce newly launched and ongoing efforts on GoAT. The ERGA Community GoAT worksheet enables ERGA Members to do this in a simple and coordinated manner.

These recommendations for announcing community genome projects are based on the 2025 v2.6 [GoAT submission guidelines](#), here tailored specifically to address the needs of ERGA Members.

🕒 At what stages can a genome project be announced?

The earlier in the process the better, but you can add your European species to the ERGA Community GoAT worksheet at any ongoing stage of reference genome generation:

- ★ You have just started working on a new project to sequence one or more reference genomes and you have finalised the set of species you will be working on.
- ★ You have already started your sampling, DNA extractions, and library preparations and you are already or will soon be generating sequencing data.
- ★ You have produced all the raw data you need and have started the assembly phase to produce the first contig-level and then scaffolded genome assembly.
- ★ You have a completed assembly and you are working on analysing it but you have not yet deposited it in an open assembly repository such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

🕒 What information do I need to prepare to add my species?

The required information for each species includes (i) summary species details; (ii) the target category; and (iii) the current status of progress; all to be provided in a standard format as a new row for each species added in the GoaT spreadsheet (note that some details may change in 2026):

- ★ The NCBI taxonomy identifier ([NCBI taxon ID](#)) for your species. If your species does not have an NCBI taxon ID assigned to it, you will need to request one following the [ENA guidelines](#) (the ERGA Secretariat can help you with this if needed).
- ★ The species name. This is the Linnean binomial species name: Generic (Genus) and specific (species) epithet, respectively. Please use the full binomial Linnean name, e.g. *Drosophila melanogaster*. Unresolved names cannot be accepted, unless they have been assigned an NCBI taxon ID (the ERGA Secretariat can help you with this if needed).
- ★ The family name: Please use the family scientific name from the [NCBI Taxonomy](#).
- ★ The target category of your species: the [GoaT submission guidelines](#) currently allow three levels. ERGA Members should indicate “other_priority” unless the species has been declared by the EBP as a target representative of a family, in which case please indicate “family_representative”.
- ★ The current status of progress: the [GoaT submission guidelines](#) currently allow seven statuses or leaving the field empty, they give an indication of the progress towards assembly and release –
 - **blank/empty** = this indicates that the project to produce the reference genome for the species has been launched but no sample(s) have yet been collected;
 - **“sample_collected”** = this indicates that at least some sample(s) has/have been collected for the species that will be used to extract DNA to generate sequencing data;
 - **“sample_acquired”** = this indicates that the sample(s) has/have been received by the laboratory where the DNA extractions will occur, e.g. a sequencing centre;
 - **“data_generation”** = this indicates that the sequencing steps have started and raw data generation (e.g. long-read or Hi-C data) is underway;
 - **“in_assembly”** = this indicates that data generation is complete and now the data are being assembled and curated to produce the reference genome;
 - **“open”** = this indicates that the assembly is openly available to the community but it has not yet been submitted to the ENA;
 - **“insdc_open”** = this indicates that the assembly is openly available on the ENA (or other International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration INSDC database). For

ERGA Community Genomes these should be included in the umbrella BioProject dedicated to collect ERGA-related genomes [PRJEB66264](#);

- “**published**” = this indicates you have a publication that reports the genome assembly of the species, i.e. you have published the genome and an associated manuscript such as a [Genome Report](#).

★ In cases where your species is known by a name not used by the NCBI taxonomy, you can provide this alternative synonym in a dedicated column of the GoAT spreadsheet.

★ If you have published a manuscript describing your genome assembly you can provide an identifier that uniquely links to the publication (in order of preference): DOI: enter the complete string, e.g. 10.1038/s44185-024-00054-6 PubMed ID (PMID) using simple numbers, e.g. 39289538 or PubMed CentralID (PMCID) including the PMC prefix, e.g. PMC11408602

🕒 How do I access the GoAT sheet to share my information?

★ The ERGA-COM GoAT sheet is viewable here [ERGA-COMMUNITY_species_goat](#)

★ To add rows to the spreadsheet you will first need to request EDIT ACCESS: (1) click on the “View only button”; (2) Click on “Request edit access”; (3) Write a short message requesting access and giving your name and country; (4) Press the “Send” button. The ERGA Secretariat will respond to your request at the earliest possible opportunity.

★ **IMPORTANT:** do not edit any header information such as column names, do not add any columns. This is because the information contained in the spreadsheet is read by a script to collect the data and send it to GoAT for processing.

★ **IMPORTANT:** do not edit any information entered by others, please only add new row(s) for your species or update the information for your species.

- ★ **Columns A to H** – you may complete the information you have collected for your species by starting a new row below the last entry, entering: **A, required** - ncbi_taxon_id; **B, required** - species; **C, optional** - subspecies; **D, required** - family; **E, required** - target_list_status; **F, required** - sequencing_status; **G, optional** - synonym; and **H, optional** - publication_id.
- ★ **Columns J to L** – please complete the extra information selecting (J) “Country Contact Email” the country where your institution is located; adding your name(s) under (K) “Responsible Person(s)”; and indicating the date you last updated this row ... double click (L) “Date Last Updated” for a calendar pop-up. **CONSENT:** By adding your name here you acknowledge that the sheet is publicly viewable and you consent to your name being openly visible.

⦿ What else do I need to do once I have announced my species?

- ★ After allowing at least two days to pass, please check the ERGA-COM page at GoaT to see if your species now appears there: <https://goat.genomehubs.org/projects/ERGA-COM>. If your species does not appear, please contact the ERGA Secretariat for assistance.
- ★ When the status of any of your species changes, you are kindly asked to revisit the sheet and update the information in the relevant columns, i.e. normally just the following two columns: (F) **sequencing_status** and (L) **Date Last Updated**.

Special cases to consider

- ★ **Species versus subspecies and name changes:** The subspecies name - if your project specifically targets a subspecies, please provide the accepted subspecies epithet. If a subspecies is valid, then it should have an NCBI Taxon ID. If the subspecies is not valid then please use the species Taxon ID. If you are unsure, please contact the ERGA Secretariat for assistance.